

GFA - GWCT - AMAST NETWORK

23 OCTOBER 2025, THE ALLERTON PROJECT

ANTIMICROBIAL USE AND RESISTANCE IN GAME BIRD PRODUCTION A TRANSDISCIPLINARY FORUM REPORT

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The workshop "Antimicrobial Use and Resistance in Game Bird Production" held on 23 October 2025 at the Game & Wildlife Conservation Trust's Allerton Project brought together 25 stakeholders from across the game bird sector in England and Wales, including producers, gamekeepers, veterinarians, researchers, and sector representatives. The goal was to address antimicrobial use (AMU) challenges in game bird production, identify opportunities for responsible stewardship, and develop collaborative strategies that support both bird health and environmental sustainability.

The meeting format combined structured presentations with facilitated breakout discussion sessions, allowing for dialogue between diverse stakeholders representing different perspectives within the game bird production system.

Participants highlighted that game bird production faces unique challenges that distinguish it from other poultry sectors, including seasonal production patterns, outdoor rearing systems, and the role of game birds in conservation and habitat management.

The sector has made progress in understanding disease patterns, particularly enteric diseases, and continues to work collaboratively with veterinary specialists and researchers to address ongoing challenges with conditions such as motile protozoa and bacterial enteritis. Reflecting the complex disease challenges inherent to outdoor production systems, the sector has demonstrated substantial commitment to responsible antimicrobial use, achieving a notable 49% reduction from 20 tonnes (2016) to 10.3 tonnes annually in 2024. The sector maintains constructive, collaborative engagement with regulatory bodies and public health stakeholders to drive evidence-based improvements, with particular focus on persistent disease and diagnostic challenges that constrain further reductions in usage.

Key challenges identified included limited diagnostic capabilities, knowledge gaps about enteric disease epidemiology, financial and institutional pressures driving antibiotic use, workforce training needs, and the complex relationship between gut microbiome health, environmental stressors, and disease susceptibility. While disease may manifest differently during game production, some challenges such as diagnostic uncertainty and resource availability for research, are common and shared with other livestock sectors.

A profound sentiment that was shared by multiple participants was that *'once spironucleus arrives in a setting, it is hard to get away from and return to normal stewardship practices'*. Furthermore, the uncertainties around motile protozoa diagnosis and treatment may only reinforce higher antimicrobial usage (AMU) in some scenarios, hence the need for research to convert some of the uncertainties into known attributes of the disease, and support more effective prevention and treatment options.

This report synthesises the key messages, challenges, and opportunities identified during the forum and outlines proposed directions for research, sector initiatives, and policy considerations. While development of new best practices is ongoing, these insights will inform the development of targeted research priorities and support tools to advocate for sector needs while promoting responsible antimicrobial stewardship in game bird production.

Appendices 1-4 contain: the meeting agenda; key messages from breakout sessions covering producer, prescriber, and research perspectives; and detailed themes from discussions.

CURRENT STATE OF ANTIMICROBIAL USE

The game bird sector in the UK represents a significant component of rural land management and the shooting sector, with production involving both game farms (hatching and rearing poults) and shoots (releasing and managing birds for sporting purposes). Understanding the current state of antimicrobial use requires consideration of the sector's unique characteristics and the disease challenges that drive treatment decisions.

SECTOR CHARACTERISTICS

Game bird production differs significantly from commercial poultry production in several aspects:

- Production is highly seasonal, with birds hatched in spring, reared and released through summer, for the shooting season in autumn/winter.
- By necessity (to ensure birds are sufficiently "hardened off" prior to release), virtually all birds are reared in outdoor systems that present different environmental and disease challenges compared to intensive indoor housing.
- The sector primarily involves pheasants and red-legged partridges, each with distinct health challenges and management requirements.
- Production involves both integrated game farms and smaller, independent shoots with varying levels of veterinary support.
- Game bird production is intrinsically linked to habitat management, predator control, and broader conservation outcomes.

ANTIMICROBIAL USE

The game bird sector actively participates in RUMA's (Responsible Use of Medicines in Agriculture) Targets Task Force framework, demonstrating transparency and commitment to antimicrobial stewardship. The sector has achieved substantial progress in reducing usage, decreasing from 20 tonnes in 2016 to 10.3 tonnes in 2024, a 49% reduction that reflects serious industry commitment. To note, other sectors collect mg/kg (AMU/animal mass), where game production collects gross AMU tonnage by virtue of dispersed outdoor rearing where birds are released prior to reaching full growth. While unique production characteristics and disease challenges mean per-kilogram metrics differ from housed livestock systems, the sector continues to pursue evidence-based strategies for further responsible reductions.

The sector's use of critically important antibiotics reflects the limited number of licensed treatments available for game birds and the specific disease challenges faced in outdoor production systems. The sector recognises the importance of judicious use of these medicines and is actively working with veterinary professionals and researchers to identify alternatives and refine treatment protocols.

However, workshop participants emphasised that RUMA and government bodies have approached this situation constructively. Regulators recognise the complexity of disease management in game bird production and support collaborative efforts to understand and address the drivers of antimicrobial use, provided the sector demonstrates ongoing commitment to improvement and research.

DISEASE CHALLENGES

Several disease challenges drive antimicrobial use in game bird production

Hexamitiasis (Hexamita/Spiroucleosis)

Caused by the protozoan parasite *Hexamita (Spiroucleus) meleagridis*, this disease causes enteritis, weight loss, and mortality, particularly in young poults. Protozoal disease is considered a major driver of antimicrobial use (particularly of tiamulin, doxycycline and similar tetracyclines); veterinary observations suggest a more nuanced picture. Some high antimicrobial user sites rarely encounter hexamitiasis, experiencing instead general gut health issues, dysbiosis, and enteritis. This suggests that hexamitiasis may exacerbate existing gut health problems rather than representing the primary driver of disease in all cases.

Remarkably consistent seasonal patterns have emerged from Yorkshire and greater Northern England, where veterinarians reported hexamitiasis appearing precisely on the first week of June over six consecutive years, suggesting strong environmental or management triggers that warrant further investigation.

Veterinary practitioners described hexamitiasis as endemic in many game bird operations, with clinical signs often appearing when birds are stressed by factors such as poor weather, feed changes, or movement.

Participants consistently emphasised that hexamitiasis is both persistent and difficult to control once established in a rearing environment. This entrenched nature, combined with ongoing uncertainty around accurate diagnosis, disease triggers, and optimal treatment approaches, can lead to reliance on antimicrobial use at critical decision points. The workshop therefore highlighted a shared need for research that clarifies the biology, epidemiology, and therapeutic options for hexamita, enabling producers and veterinarians to adopt more confident, evidence-based stewardship practices while reducing avoidable antimicrobial exposure.

Coccidiosis

Coccidiosis is another gut protozoal infection, which is a recurring problem in game bird farming. This infection not only causes disease itself but also damages the gut environment, thus predisposing birds to secondary infections like hexamita. The interaction between coccidia and other gut diseases would benefit from deeper investigation and could be a key factor in driving antimicrobial use.

Enteric diseases, dysbiosis and gut microbiome

Enteritis caused by bacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, *Clostridium* species, and others, require treatment with antimicrobials including oxytetracycline and amprolium. These bacterial infections may be primary conditions or secondary to other stressors or protozoan infections.

Unpublished research presented by Benjamin South and Martha Betson at the workshop has revealed unexpected complexity in the game bird gut microbiome and its relationship to enteric disease. Pioneering work by a group of gamebird vets in collaboration with Surrey University has begun to challenge assumptions about the causative agents of enteric disease.

Using 16S rRNA gene sequencing to map bacterial communities and metaprotocol sequencing to identify protozoal populations, researchers discovered the presence of Chilomastix, a motile protozoan not previously recognised as significant in game birds. While Chilomastix is considered non-pathogenic in chickens, experimental infections produce symptoms including anorexia, diarrhoea, poor growth, and mortality, which are precisely the clinical signs observed in diseased game birds. Critically, Chilomastix forms environmentally resistant cysts similar to coccidia, potentially explaining the persistent nature of enteric problems on some sites. This discovery raises fundamental questions about disease causation and appropriate treatment approaches.

Workshop participants consider dysbiosis (disruption of the normal gut bacterial community) a central factor in disease susceptibility. Environmental stressors, dietary changes, coccidial infections, and viral diseases can trigger bacterial community shifts that create conditions for pathogenic organisms to flourish. The relationship between gut microbiome diversity, stability, and disease resistance emerged as a critical area requiring further research.

While environmental management practices and interventions to reduce disease incidence are increasingly implemented in the sector, critical knowledge gaps remain about the fundamental biology of Spironucleus itself. Understanding how the organism invades the gut, what triggers progression from colonisation to clinical disease, and the organism's life cycle (including whether it has an encysted form) remains elusive.

DATA AND MONITORING

The game bird sector has made important progress in antimicrobial surveillance and data collection, primarily through voluntary, sector-driven schemes with improved participation. While gaps and challenges remain, particularly with achieving 100% coverage, these efforts have significantly improved understanding of usage patterns and supported responsible management of antibiotics in the sector. The sector is working to develop comprehensive antimicrobial use monitoring systems that will enable more detailed tracking of usage patterns, identification of best practices, and benchmarking of performance. Enhanced data collection will strengthen the sector's ability to demonstrate stewardship progress to regulators and stakeholders and will provide valuable insights to guide targeted interventions and support continuous improvement across the sector.

REGULATORY CONTEXT

The regulatory environment for antimicrobial use in game bird production has evolved significantly in recent years. Veterinarians must navigate the prescribing cascade (a hierarchical system that permits use of medicines licensed for other species when no suitable licensed product exists for game birds) when medicines licensed specifically for game birds are unavailable. Furthermore, the classification of game birds as food-producing animals affects medicine availability and withdrawal periods.

These regulatory factors create uncertainty for both producers and prescribers, particularly regarding continued access to effective treatments for endemic diseases like hexamitiasis.

KEY CHALLENGES IDENTIFIED

Forum participants identified barriers across several critical areas that collectively prevent optimal antimicrobial stewardship and bird health outcomes. Many of these challenges reflect both systemic issues within the game bird sector and operational realities faced by individual businesses, while some general challenges such as resource availability and diagnostic uncertainty are shared with other sectors.

LIMITED UNDERSTANDING OF DISEASE EPIDEMIOLOGY AND BIOLOGY

Workshop participants emphasised fundamental knowledge gaps about disease causation, transmission, and epidemiology in game bird production. While veterinarians recognise clinical disease patterns, the underlying microbial communities, their ecological relationships, and environmental triggers remain poorly characterised.

While hexamitiasis is recognised as endemic in outdoor production systems, research is needed to better understand transmission pathways, particularly whether vertical transmission occurs and the role of environmental contamination. The contribution of wild birds to disease transmission and maintenance in game bird populations also requires further investigation to inform targeted prevention strategies.

The observation of unexpected organisms such as *Chilomastix* in diseased birds illustrates how current assumptions about disease agents may be incomplete or incorrect. Without understanding of which organisms drive disease, when they colonise birds, and what environmental or management factors influence their pathogenicity, targeted prevention and treatment strategies remain elusive.

While stress is recognised as important, the specific factors that trigger clinical disease in colonised birds need better characterisation.

LOGISTICAL DELAYS IN ACCESSING TREATMENT

Logistical challenges in accessing veterinary support and obtaining medicated feed following disease onset (and overall during disease outbreaks) can impact treatment timing and outcomes. The sector is exploring solutions including improved veterinary service coverage, enhanced producer-veterinarian communication systems, and health planning approaches that enable more rapid response to disease challenges while maintaining appropriate veterinary oversight and responsible prescribing practices.

Administration of soluble treatment via water is not always possible in release pens although considerable effort is being made to widen the availability of this option, which allows for immediate treatment in most cases.

PRESCRIBING CASCADE AND MEDICINE AVAILABILITY

Workshop participants highlighted that prescribing decisions in game bird production are frequently shaped by the limited number of veterinary medicines licensed specifically for this sector, particularly for enteric and protozoal diseases. In practice, this means that veterinarians often rely on the prescribing cascade, not because suitable medicines are entirely unavailable, but because licensed, game bird-specific options are few. It was also noted that some commonly used coccidiostats in other poultry sectors, such as ionophores, are regulated as feed additives rather than veterinary medicines and therefore sit outside the prescribing cascade, which may not always be clearly understood by all stakeholders.

While a range of products may be accessible under the cascade, participants noted that its use introduces additional complexity, including longer and more variable withdrawal periods linked to the classification of game birds as food-producing animals, requirements for explicit clinical justification, and a perceived risk of regulatory scrutiny on appropriate usage. These factors can create uncertainty among both prescribers and producers about what is permissible and practical, particularly in time-critical outbreak situations.

Concerns were also raised about future access to effective treatments for hexamitiasis, where reliance on a narrow set of therapeutic options leaves the sector vulnerable should availability change.

Overall, the challenge identified was not an absence of medicines per se, but a combination of limited game bird-specific licensing, uncertainty around cascade use, and practical constraints that can delay or complicate timely, confident prescribing decisions.

DIAGNOSTIC LIMITATIONS

The rapid progression of diseases such as hexamitiasis presents diagnostic challenges that the sector is actively working to address. Veterinarians combine clinical expertise with post-mortem examination and laboratory testing to guide treatment decisions. Workshop participants identified the development of rapid, field-deployable diagnostic tools as a priority that would enable more targeted antimicrobial use, and emphasised the value of enhanced laboratory services with shorter turnaround times to support evidence-based treatment during disease outbreaks.

Microscopic examination can identify motile protozoa but cannot definitively distinguish between species or determine pathogenicity. Advanced molecular diagnostic approaches (18S sequencing, metabarcoding) remain research tools rather than routine clinical diagnostics, limiting their application in real-world disease management.

Variability in access to specialised veterinary services and diagnostics is pronounced, especially for smaller operations that may not have regular vet visits. Many rely on general practitioners with less specific experience or slower response times.

The compressed timeline of game bird rearing, with narrow windows for intervention before the shooting season, makes diagnostic delays particularly consequential, often forcing empirical treatment decisions with broad-spectrum antimicrobials.

FINANCIAL STAKES AND EMOTIONAL PRESSURE

Game bird production represents substantial investment for farmers and shoot operators, while gamekeepers' livelihoods depend on successful bird presentation.

Workshop participants discussed the significant investments involved in game bird production and the genuine economic impacts of disease outbreaks on farming businesses and rural employment. Veterinarians work within these realities to balance animal health and welfare needs, professional stewardship principles, and relationships with their clients that support rural livelihoods.

The sector recognises that addressing these complex dynamics through improved disease prevention, rapid diagnostics, and evidence-based treatment protocols will support both responsible antimicrobial use and sustainable business operations.

SEASONAL TIMELINE CONSTRAINTS

Game bird production operates on an annual cycle where timelines are dictated by the breeding and shooting season and predicated by the weather at that time. Poor and variable weather, such as very cold nights followed by warmer days, likely contributes to poor health status of the birds, increasing the need for treatment being necessary. Disease outbreaks during the rearing period leave limited time for recovery before birds must be released, creating urgency that may favour rapid antimicrobial intervention over slower preventive approaches or diagnostic investigation.

This compressed timeline also complicates research efforts, as each year provides only a narrow sampling window. Opportunities to collect samples and test interventions are limited, and multi-year studies are essential but challenging to sustain.

TRAINING AND SKILLS DEVELOPMENT

Workforce training is a critical factor in disease prevention and antimicrobial stewardship. Gamekeepers and farm staff require knowledge of biosecurity practices, early disease recognition, environmental management, and the principles underlying responsible antimicrobial use.

However, the sector faces challenges in providing consistent, accessible training opportunities. The seasonal nature of employment, geographic dispersal of operations, and time constraints during busy rearing periods all complicate skills development efforts.

COMMUNICATION BETWEEN STAKEHOLDERS

Workshop discussions emphasised the importance of effective communication between farmers, keepers, veterinarians, and researchers. However, participants noted that current communication pathways may not always facilitate the knowledge transfer needed for optimal decision-making. Research findings must reach practitioners in accessible formats, while clinical observations from the field should inform research priorities.

PUBLIC PERCEPTION

The sector benefits from constructive, collaborative relationships with RUMA and VMD, who recognise the genuine disease challenges faced in game bird production and support evidence-based approaches to stewardship.

Workshop participants emphasised the importance of transparent communication about antimicrobial use to stakeholders and the public, ensuring that sector practices are understood within their proper scientific and welfare context.

While antimicrobial use in game bird production addresses genuine animal health and welfare needs, opportunities exist for continued optimisation of usage. The sector is committed to building a robust evidence base through research that clarifies disease mechanisms, validates treatment approaches, and identifies opportunities for reduction while maintaining bird health and welfare.

OPPORTUNITIES AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The challenges identified throughout the forum discussions point toward opportunities for collaborative action that could further advance antimicrobial stewardship while supporting sustainable game bird production, set against the ongoing development of best practices.

These recommendations reflect input from producers, veterinarians, researchers, and sector representatives, and emphasise practical and achievable approaches. All studies should be initiated from and informed by the existing experience and expertise of keepers, farmers and estates, where knowledge on best practices and challenges is already established.

COMPREHENSIVE HEALTH AND GUT MICROBIOME STUDIES

Workshop participants identified comprehensive longitudinal studies of the game bird gut microbiome as a foundational research priority. Such studies should characterise:

- Normal microbial community composition throughout the rearing cycle
- When different organisms colonise birds and under what circumstances
- Relationships between bacterial communities and protozoal populations
- How environmental factors, dietary changes, and stressors influence microbiome stability and persistence of pathogenic organisms
- The role of maternal transmission in early gut colonisation
- Environmental sources and persistence of pathogenic organisms

This work would sustain investment beyond short-term projects. A three-year PhD programme was identified as the optimal vehicle for conducting rigorous, comprehensive microbiome research while training the next generation of specialists in this field. This could be extended to five years with a post-doctoral researcher involved, if the appropriate funding was available.

DISEASE EPIDEMIOLOGY AND TRANSMISSION

Understanding disease epidemiology requires systematic investigation of:

- Seasonal patterns in disease emergence and their environmental and climactic triggers
- Transmission routes for key pathogens (vertical vs horizontal, environmental persistence)
- Risk factors that predict disease susceptibility at farm and flock levels, including those factors that are common across sites
- Interaction effects between multiple pathogens (viruses, coccidia, bacteria, protozoa)
- Validation of clinical diagnostic criteria against molecular confirmation
- Identification of symptoms (e.g. enteritis) that may be an indicator of hexamita disease onset or secondary infection, allowing for initiation of earlier treatment.

REGULATORY AND POLICY ENGAGEMENT

- Maintaining constructive dialogue with RUMA, government veterinary services, and public health authorities helps ensure that regulatory approaches recognise sector-specific challenges while supporting continued improvement.
- Regulatory engagement is a major theme discussed in the meeting when it comes to accessing necessary medicines, especially newer or alternative therapies like certain coccidiostats or feed additives that are already approved in other sectors but not yet available for game birds. Veterinarians are keenly interested in having logical treatments that match the etiology and manifestation of parasitic disease.

CONCLUSION & NEXT STEPS

The workshop "Antimicrobial Use and Resistance in Game Bird Production" successfully brought together diverse perspectives from across the game bird sector to address antimicrobial stewardship challenges. The transdisciplinary forum format enabled productive dialogue between producers, veterinarians, researchers, and industry representatives, generating insights that reflect the sector's unique characteristics and operational realities. Participants demonstrated both recognition of the urgency of antimicrobial stewardship and commitment to evidence-based solutions.

Key messages emerging from the workshop include:

- Fundamental knowledge gaps about disease epidemiology and gut microbiome ecology must be addressed through sustained, comprehensive research
- Recent discoveries challenge assumptions about disease causation and suggest that current treatment approaches may not always target the most relevant pathogens
- Financial and emotional pressures on stakeholders influence prescribing decisions and must be acknowledged in developing realistic stewardship strategies
- Improved diagnostics, alternative treatments, and workforce development all represent important components of a comprehensive approach
- The sector's antimicrobial usage, particularly of critically important antibiotics, creates vulnerability to public criticism and regulatory intervention
- Collaborative, transdisciplinary approaches that bring together producers, veterinarians, and researchers offer the best path forward

The forum identified both immediate opportunities for action and longer-term priorities requiring sustained effort and resources:

- Develop funding proposals for comprehensive gut health and microbiome veterinary research and/or clinical epidemiologic research, ideally structured as a three-year PhD programme
- Establish mechanisms for ongoing stakeholder engagement and knowledge sharing
- Create practical guidance documents translating current evidence into actionable recommendations for producers and veterinarians (e.g., decision support tools)
- Develop training programmes covering biosecurity, disease recognition, and responsible antimicrobial use
- Support pilot projects evaluating alternative approaches to disease prevention and treatment
- Strengthen data collection and monitoring systems to track progress and identify areas requiring targeted intervention

The game bird sector demonstrates strong commitment to responsible antimicrobial stewardship while maintaining the highest standards of bird health and welfare.

Through the collaborative, transdisciplinary approach demonstrated at this forum, the sector is actively advancing toward sustainable production systems that responsibly minimise antimicrobial use through evidence-based strategies, while supporting the health of game bird populations and the broader conservation, habitat management, and recreational values they provide.

APPENDIX 1 - MEETING AGENDA

9:30 - 10:00: **Arrival & Registration** - Coffee, tea, and bacon rolls

10:00 - 10:15: **Welcome & Introduction** - Dominic Boulton (GFA) & Matt Gilmour (AMAST Network)

10:15 - 10:25: **Setting the Scene** - Paul Jevons, GFA President & RUMA Targets Task Force Representative

Session 1: The Producer Perspective - Practical Realities On-Farm

- 10:25 - 10:30: The Game Farmer's View – Paul Jevons, GFA President
- 10:30 - 10:35: The Gamekeeper's Perspective - Gareth Clark, Chairman, Greater Exmoor Shoot Association
- 10:35 - 11:00: Breakout Session - Small group discussions with guide questions
- 11:00 - 11:15: Plenary Feedback - Key themes and insights from group discussions
- 11:15 - 11:30: BREAK - Coffee, tea, and refreshments

Session 2: The Prescriber Perspective - Veterinary Expertise & Evidence

- 11:30 - 11:35: Veterinary Perspective - Alan Beynon, St David's Game Bird Services (Head of Practice)
- 11:35 - 11:40: Veterinary Perspective - Ian Jones, Game Bird Veterinarian
- 11:40 - 12:10: Breakout Session
- 12:10 - 12:30: Plenary Feedback
- 12:30 - 14:00: LUNCH & FARM TOUR - Lunch provided, followed by optional Walk Around the Allerton Project - Tour with Roger Draycott, GWCT

Session 3: Research & Innovation Perspectives

- 14:00 - 14:10: Ben South, Veterinarian & Researcher, St David's Game Bird Services
- 14:10 - 14:15: Dan King, Veterinarian & RUMA TTF Representative
- 14:15 - 14:45: Breakout Session
- 14:45 - 15:00: Plenary Feedback

15:00 - 15:20: **Synthesis, Priority Setting and Action Planning** - Dominic Boulton (GFA) & Matt Gilmour (AMAST Network)

15:20 - 15:30: **Closing Remarks** - George Davis, GFA Chairman

APPENDIX 2 - PRODUCER PERSPECTIVE

CURRENT DISEASE CHALLENGES

- Hexamitiasis is universally identified as the most significant disease challenge, with producers describing it as endemic in game bird production. Clinical signs typically appear at 4-6 weeks of age once the birds spend more time outdoors, so is often triggered by stress factors including weather changes, feed transitions, or movement. Between weeks 7-10 is when the highest incidence of disease is observed.
- Coccidiosis is a persistent and influential disease in game bird production that drives much of the medication and management strategies discussed in the sector. It prompts both direct use of anticoccidial drugs and indirectly increases antibiotic use due to its impact on gut health and its synergy with other pathogens like hexamita. The effectiveness of coccidiosis control is influenced by factors such as management practices, strain variation, environmental stress, and limitations on which drugs are licensed for use in game birds.
- Secondary bacterial infections (bacterial enteritis), particularly E. coli, often occur alongside or following hexamitiasis, requiring additional antimicrobial intervention. When birds are affected by protozoal diseases like coccidiosis or hexamita, their gut lining is damaged. This damage creates an environment where opportunistic bacteria can invade and proliferate, leading to bacterial enteritis. Treatment of bacterial enteritis almost always requires antibiotics, as untreated infections rapidly worsen bird welfare and performance. Improved management of primary diseases and gut health is seen as key to reducing the cascade that leads to enteritis and subsequent antibiotic intervention.

CURRENT MANAGEMENT APPROACHES

- High risk factors such as poor weather and stress together with financial implications place significant pressure on game managers and vets to treat. Practical alternatives need to be found as a matter of priority.
- Rapid treatment at first signs of disease to prevent spread through the flock
- Variable implementation of biosecurity measures, with challenges in maintaining rigorous protocols in outdoor systems
- Attempts to optimise stocking density to balance production efficiency with disease risk
- Attention to providing shelter, appropriate bedding, and protection from weather where possible
- Limited choice of antimicrobials available to use in game birds

FACTORS INFLUENCING ANTIMICROBIAL USE STRUCTURE

Disease-related barriers:

- The endemic nature of hexamitiasis means that birds are likely colonised from an early age, with clinical disease triggered by stress rather than new infection
- Limited proven alternatives to antimicrobials for preventing or treating hexamitiasis and bacterial enteritis
- Difficulty obtaining rapid, definitive diagnosis that would enable more targeted treatment
- Environmental constraints:
- Inability to control weather conditions that trigger disease outbreaks
- Inherent challenges of maintaining biosecurity and controlling environmental conditions in outdoor rearing systems
- Inevitable contact with wild birds and their associated pathogens in outdoor systems

Economic factors:

- Intense price competition limits margins available for investment in disease prevention measures
- Many alternative interventions (probiotics, nutraceuticals, etc.) add significant cost without proven efficacy
- Small to medium-sized operations struggle to justify costs of diagnostic testing, specialised equipment, or infrastructure improvements

Knowledge and support:

- Lack of game bird-specific research on disease prevention and alternative management approaches
- Geographic variation in access to veterinarians with game bird expertise
- Limited formal mechanisms for sharing best practices and learning from others' experiences

PRODUCER PRIORITIES AND NEEDS

- Research into biology, aetiology, transmission, risk factors, and evidence-based prevention strategies for hexamitiasis
- Specific, achievable biosecurity recommendations tailored to outdoor game bird systems
- Strategies for mitigating disease risk during poor weather conditions
- Rigorous evaluation of alternative interventions to identify what actually works
- More affordable, rapid diagnostic options suitable for game bird production
- Medicine availability and continued access to effective treatments, particularly for hexamitiasis
- Peer learning opportunities to share experiences and learn from each other

APPENDIX 3 - PRESCRIBER PERSPECTIVE

The prescriber perspective sessions explored veterinary experiences in managing game bird health, including diagnostic challenges, treatment decisions, and opportunities for improved antimicrobial stewardship.

DIAGNOSTIC CHALLENGES

- Hexamitiasis and bacterial enteritis can present with similar clinical signs, making differentiation challenging, based on clinical observation alone
- Laboratory turnaround times may be too long to inform initial treatment decisions, forcing empirical therapy
- Obtaining good quality samples from representative cases can be difficult, particularly in extensive outdoor systems
- The cost of laboratory diagnostics can be prohibitive for some clients, particularly smaller operations
- Birds often have multiple pathogens present, making it difficult to determine which is the primary driver of clinical disease

TREATMENT DECISION-MAKING

Empirical treatment decisions:

- Selection of first-line antimicrobials typically based on clinical experience and knowledge of common pathogens
- Decisions about whether to treat entire flocks or only affected birds based on disease spread patterns and practical considerations
- Balancing adequate treatment duration against concerns about antimicrobial exposure

Factors influencing prescribing:

- More aggressive treatment approach for rapidly spreading or severe disease
- Treatment decisions influenced by bird age and production schedule
- Weather conditions and season influence disease risk and treatment urgency
- Practical ability of clients to implement different treatment approaches

PRESCRIBING CASCADE AND MEDICINE AVAILABILITY

- Few veterinary medicines are licensed specifically for game birds, and this includes limited availability of licensed coccidiostats, requiring frequent use of the prescribing cascade
- Navigating the cascade adds complexity to prescribing decisions and requires careful consideration of food-producing animal status (extended withdrawal periods for some cascade products create practical challenges)
- Particular concern about future availability of effective treatments for hexamitiasis, which could significantly impact the sector
- Delays to get a prescription after noticing the start of outbreak

ANTIMICROBIAL STEWARDSHIP OPPORTUNITIES

Diagnostic improvements:

- Development of rapid tests for hexamitiasis and key bacterial pathogens would enable more targeted treatment
- Improved laboratory access and reduced turnaround times would support diagnostic-led treatment decisions
- Encouraging more routine necropsy submissions to improve disease surveillance and diagnostic accuracy

Prevention focus:

- Greater focus on biosecurity as primary disease prevention strategy
- Husbandry optimisation to address management factors that predispose to disease
- Minimising stressors that trigger clinical disease in colonised birds
- Improving housing and environmental conditions to reduce disease pressure

Treatment refinement:

- More precise targeting of antimicrobials to affected groups rather than flock-wide treatment where appropriate
- Greater use of supportive care and non-antibiotic interventions alongside or instead of antimicrobials
- Development of evidence-based treatment protocols that optimise efficacy while minimising use

RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT NEEDS

- Better understanding of hexamitiasis epidemiology, transmission pathways, and triggers for clinical disease
- Controlled trials of alternative interventions including probiotics, prebiotics, and other non-antibiotic approaches
- Surveillance for antimicrobial resistance in game bird pathogens
- Evidence-based evaluation of management interventions for disease prevention
- Development and validation of practical diagnostic tools for field use

COLLABORATION AND KNOWLEDGE SHARING

- Peer discussion for veterinarians to discuss challenging cases and share experiences
- Specialised training and continuing professional development focused on game bird medicine, including for general practitioners
- Supporting producer education about disease recognition, prevention, and responsible antimicrobial use
- Strengthening links between veterinary practitioners and researchers to inform research priorities and facilitate applied studies
- Sector guidelines: Development of sector-wide guidelines for disease management and antimicrobial stewardship in game bird production

APPENDIX 4 - RESEARCH & INNOVATION PERSPECTIVES

The research and innovation sessions explored current knowledge, research gaps, and opportunities for advancing game bird health management through scientific investigation.

CURRENT RESEARCH ACTIVITIES

- Investigation of game bird gut microbiome composition and its relationship to health and disease susceptibility
- Studies examining the diversity of protozoan parasites in game birds and their pathogenic potential
- Ongoing surveillance of disease patterns through veterinary diagnostic laboratories and scanning surveillance programs
- Limited trials of management interventions such as probiotics and environmental modifications

PRIORITY KNOWLEDGE GAPS

Workshop participants emphasised that while research into environmental factors, stocking densities, and management practices that reduce disease incidence is valuable and should continue, approaches that address disease causation should also be prioritised. Many management interventions are already implemented in well-run operations, yet disease outbreaks persist. To move beyond empirical responses when disease occurs, the sector needs fundamental research into the organism itself and the mechanisms of disease pathogenesis.

Priority knowledge gaps include:

- Whether hexamitiasis can be transmitted vertically (from parent to offspring) or is primarily environmental/horizontal transmission
- How long the organism persists in the environment and what factors affect survival
- What specific factors trigger progression from colonization to clinical disease
- Whether there is clinically significant variation in pathogenicity between different hexamita strains or isolates
- The role of wild birds in maintaining and transmitting hexamitiasis to game bird populations
- How the organism invades intestinal tissue, whether invasion requires pre-existing gut damage or dysbiosis, what metabolic or virulence factors enable colonisation, and whether disease results from direct tissue damage, toxin production, or immune-mediated pathology

Microbiome and gut health:

- Characterisation of healthy gut microbiome composition in pheasants and partridges at different life stages
- Understanding how microbiome disruption relates to disease susceptibility and clinical illness
- How hexamitiasis and bacterial pathogens interact with the normal gut microbiome
- Whether and how the microbiome can be beneficially manipulated through probiotics, prebiotics, coccidiostats, or other interventions

Disease risk factors:

- Quantifying the impact of specific environmental conditions (temperature, humidity, wind, etc.) on disease risk
- How diet composition, feed quality, and nutritional status affect disease susceptibility
- Optimal stocking densities that balance production efficiency with disease risk
- Identifying and quantifying the various stressors that trigger clinical disease

ALTERNATIVE INTERVENTIONS

- Controlled trials of specific probiotic products under commercial conditions
- Evaluation of prebiotic compounds and synbiotic combinations
- Testing of plant-derived compounds with potential antimicrobial or immunomodulatory effects
- Assessment of efficacy of organic acids and medium-chain fatty acids for disease prevention and gut health support
- Approaches to enhancing immune function and disease resistance through immunomodulation

DIAGNOSTIC TOOL DEVELOPMENT

- Development of rapid pen-side tests for hexamitiasis and bacterial pathogens suitable for field use
- Application of PCR and other molecular methods for rapid pathogen detection
- Practical approaches to microbiome analysis that could inform health management
- Identification of biomarkers that could predict disease risk or early disease before clinical signs appear

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE

- Baseline surveillance data on antimicrobial resistance patterns in game bird bacterial pathogens
- Monitoring for emergence and changes in resistance patterns over time
- Characterisation of resistance genes present in game bird microbiomes
- Understanding how different antimicrobial use patterns affect resistance development

TRANSLATION AND IMPLEMENTATION RESEARCH

- On-farm practical trials of management interventions conducted under commercial conditions
- Cost-benefit analysis of different disease prevention and management approaches
- Understanding factors that influence adoption of best practices by producers
- Evaluating effective approaches to communicating research findings and supporting practice change

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE AND CAPACITY

- Access to facilities suitable for game bird research, including experimental infection facilities
- Growing the community of researchers with expertise in game bird health

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- Strengthening partnerships between researchers and sector to ensure research addresses practical needs
 - Identifying and accessing appropriate funding sources for game bird health research
 - Establishing systems for collecting and sharing data on disease occurrence, antimicrobial use, and management practices

INTEGRATION WITH BROADER CONSERVATION GOALS

- Understanding how habitat management practices affect game bird health
- Investigating disease transmission between game birds and wild bird populations
- Exploring connections between game bird management, antimicrobial use, and broader ecosystem health
- Framing game bird health research within One Health frameworks that consider human, animal, and environmental health

THE AMAST NETWORK, A UKRI NETWORK

AntiMicrobial Resistance in Agrifood Systems
Transdisciplinary Network

UK Research
and Innovation

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